

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{III}

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The synthesis and characterization of a series of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{III} incorporating 1,3-diketones and the Schiff base derived from ethylenediamine and salicylaldehyde (H₂Salen) have been reported. The complexes prepared are of the types 1,3-diketonato-*OO'*-[*N,N'*-ethylenebis(salicylideneiminato)]cobalt(III). The complexes have been assigned octahedral geometry on the basis of analytical and spectral data.

The chemistry of cobalt(III) complexes with 1,3-diketones has been actively pursued. The metal complexes of β -dicarbonyl donor ligands have generated great interest due to the effect of different substituents on the physicochemical properties of their complexes¹. In present investigation mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(III) were prepared by the reaction of *N,N'*-ethylenebis(salicylideneiminato)cobalt(II) i.e. [Co^{II}-Salen] complex with the corresponding β -diketone in 1 : 1 ratio. Studies reveal that the reaction of the β -diketones with the (Salen)Co^{II} complex resulted in the oxidation of Co^{II} to give Co^{III} mixed compounds. The β -diketone moiety is coordinated with the metal as a bidentate ligand to give hexa-coordinated compounds.

The following complexes were prepared :

where $\text{O} \text{---} \text{N} \text{---} \text{N} \text{---} \text{O} = [\text{O}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}(\text{:N}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{N:})\text{O}-\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_4]$
X = -H, -CH₃, -F, -Cl, -Br, -OCH₃, -OH, -NH₂, -NO₂, -OC₂H₅

Spectral studies :

The IR spectra of the (Salen)Co^{II} complex show the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ bands in the region 1620 cm^{-1} . The (Salen)Co^{III} (β -diketone) complex show addition bands attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ around 1580 cm^{-1} and 1540 cm^{-1} , respectively². This is consistent with the *O,O'*-coordination of the diaryl-1,3-diketone and the formation of hexa-

coordinated mixed complex.

The electronic spectra observed are consistent with an octahedral geometry and formation of diamagnetic cobalt(III) complexes. Two bands observed in the electronic spectra of the mixed complexes around 570 nm and 630 nm have assigned to split components of the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition². This splitting is attributed to the lowering of the octahedral symmetry due to the presence of different ligand. The band at 380 nm have been assigned to an intra ligand transition. The characterization data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The ¹H NMR of the uncoordinated diaryl- β -diketones show the signal for methine protons in the range of δ 6.6–6.8 and enolic proton at δ 16.6⁷. The ¹H NMR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes show the absence of signal at δ 16.6 for the enolic proton of the free β -diketones, an upfield shift of =CH- signal (δ 6.1–6.5) is observed probably due to electron delocalisation in the chelate ring system. A singlet is obtained for dioxymethylene protons at δ 5.9–6.1². A complicated pattern was observed in the aromatic region. The signal for the methylene protons of the coordinated Schiff base is observed as a singlet at δ 3.5–4.0. These observations are consistent with *O,O'* complexation of the diketone and the formation of hexa-coordinated Co^{III} mixed ligand complex¹.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer infracord 577 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were taken in CDCl₃ on Jeol 90 MHz FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Electronic spectra were recorded on SP 8-100 Pye Unicam spectrophotometer.

Table 1. Characterization data of title compounds

Compd.	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Analysis (%)				M.p. (°C)	IR bands (cm ⁻¹)			¹ H NMR (δ ppm)		
			Calcd. (Found)					ν(C=N)	ν(C≡O)	ν(C≡C)	=C-H	OCH ₂ O	Aromatic
			C	H	N	Co							
1a	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₂ Co	592	64.86 (64.53)	4.22 (4.01)	4.73 (4.46)	9.97 (9.71)	123	1612	1580	1530	6.2	5.9	6.6–7.9
1b	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₂ Co	606	65.35 (65.11)	4.46 (4.22)	4.62 (4.50)	9.74 (9.63)	178	1620	1585	1530	6.3	6.0	6.6–7.9
1c	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₂ FCo	610	62.95 (62.81)	3.93 (3.77)	4.59 (4.41)	9.67 (9.54)	190	1675	1583	1542	6.2	6.0	6.5–7.8
1d	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₂ ClCo	626.5	61.29 (61.06)	3.83 (3.72)	4.47 (4.29)	9.42 (9.23)	197	1615	1580	1526	6.3	6.1	6.5–7.9
1e	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₂ BrCo	670	57.31 (57.02)	3.58 (3.44)	4.18 (4.03)	8.81 (8.69)	162	1618	1580	1530	6.3	6.0	6.5–8.0
1f	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₂ Co	622	63.67 (63.35)	4.34 (4.16)	4.50 (4.32)	9.49 (9.35)	186	1618	1585	1526	6.5	6.1	6.6–8.0
1g	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₂ Co	608	63.16 (62.98)	4.11 (3.98)	4.61 (4.45)	9.70 (9.57)	159	1620	1585	1532	6.5	6.0	6.5–8.0
1h	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₃ Co	607	63.26 (63.09)	4.28 (4.08)	6.92 (6.79)	9.72 (9.58)	142	1618	1583	1530	6.4	5.9	6.6–7.9
1i	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₃ Co	637	60.28 (59.97)	3.78 (3.60)	6.59 (6.46)	9.26 (9.15)	173	1620	1590	1526	6.5	6.1	6.6–8.1
1j	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₂ Co	636	64.15 (63.96)	4.56 (4.39)	4.40 (4.21)	9.28 (9.11)	151	1620	1585	1532	6.3	6.1	6.5–8.0

Generalized preparation of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(III) :

The 1,3-diketones (propane-1-(1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)-3-phenyl-1,3-dione) were prepared by reported method³. (Salen)Co^{II} was prepared by reported methods⁴. To a 50 ml of ethanolic solution of (Salen)Co^{II} (0.0015 M), β-diketone (0.003 M) was added⁵. The mixture was refluxed for one hour. After cooling, the green crystals were filtered and dried. The purity was checked by TLC using benzene : acetone (9 : 1) as mobile phase.

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